

The Influence of Work Experience and Employee Competency on Nurse Performance

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ABSTRACT

Human Resource Management (HRM) is a science or method of managing the relationships and roles of resources (workforce) owned by individuals efficiently and effectively. HR management consists of HR planning, personnel selection, training and development, and performance assessment. The performance of nurses in hospitals is very important because it can influence performance in achieving health services in the hospital itself. This study aims to determine and analyze the influence of work experience and competency on the performance of nurses at RSD dr. Soebandi Jember. The data used in this research is primary data obtained through distributing questionnaires. The population in this study were all nurses at RSD dr. Soebandi, numbering 463 people. The sampling technique or method used was stratified random sampling, totaling 150 people. Validity and reliability analysis was carried out in this research. Hypothesis testing is also carried out for direct influence analysis. The research results stated that work experience had a significant effect on nurse performance. Nurse competency has a significant effect on nurse performance.

KEYWORDS: Work experience, nurse competency, performance, hospital.

INTRODUCTON

Human Resource Management (HRM) is a science or method of managing the relationships and roles of resources (workforce) owned by individuals efficiently and effectively and can be used optimally so that common goals between the company, employees and society are achieved (Irmayani, 2021 ; Main, 2020). HR management consists of HR planning, personnel selection, training and development, and performance assessment (Azhad et al., 2015). Employee performance is something that is very important because a decrease in performance in an organization can have a significant impact on the sustainability of an organization. so that in this case a leader has quite a tough task where he must always try to improve his performance and provide motivation for his subordinates so they can improve their performance to achieve organizational goals (Mangkunegara, 2019). Employee performance needs to be improved by any organization in facing increasing business competition. To improve performance, there are many factors that influence it. One of the factors indicated to improve performance is work experience and employee competence.

Work experience can be interpreted as a learning process to form skills regarding the methods of a job and

can be assessed by the time span of how long one has worked. All the lessons learned by a person from the events he or she carries out in the course of his or her life are referred to as work experience (Siagian, 2015). According to (Manullang, 2012), usually someone can gain experience directly or indirectly. Work experience is the process of forming an employee's knowledge about the work patterns he or she carries out. Employees who have work experience are usually experts in carrying out the tasks given to them. Thus it can be concluded that work experience can improve performance. Research conducted by (Bili et al., 2018) states that there is a positive and significant influence between work experience on employee performance at the Laham District Office, Mahakam Ulu Regency, with a correlation of 0.049. Research conducted by (Dash et al., 2017) states that work experience has an impact on compensation performance. Other research which also discusses the issue of the relationship between work experience which states that there is an influence on performance was carried out by: (Arifin & Putra, 2020; Dewanti & Artaya, 2019; Kim et al., 2009; Masriah, 2021; Prasetya, 2018; Rivaldo & Nabella, 2023; Sinambela & Ernawati, 2021; W. Wahyudi, 2018), (Ardianto, 2020; Ratnawati et al., 2020). Meanwhile, research from (Nyoman

et al., 2023) states that work experience has no impact on employee performance.

Competence can also be said to be a factor that can improve employee performance in a company organization. If in an organization there is an employee who has high competence such as knowledge, skills, abilities and attitudes that are appropriate to the position he or she holds, then that employee is always encouraged to work effectively, efficiently and productively (Qomariah, 2020). According to (Hutapea, 2008), the definition of competency is knowledge, skills, abilities and personal characteristics that directly influence a person's performance. With competent employees, the work assigned can be completed on time. Thus it can be concluded that competency can improve employee performance. Research conducted by (Basriani, 2016) states that competence influences performance. Other research that also discusses the issue of the relationship between competencies with positive results was conducted by: (Renyut et al., 2017), (Abusama et al., 2017), (Kotamena et al., 2020; Marhayani et al., 2019), (Adam & Kamase, 2019; Amdani et al., 2019; Bahri et al., 2018; Friolina et al., 2017; Indiyarningsih et al., 2020; Manik & Syafrina, 2018; Mukhtar, 2018; Mustikawati & Qomariah, 2020; Nyoto et al., 2020; Yamin & Ishak, 2018), (Marhayani et al., 2019), (Basriani, 2016).), (Kotamena et al., 2020), (Anggriawan et al., 2023). Meanwhile, research conducted by (Chandra et al., 2020), (Utomo et al., 2019) states that competence has no influence on employee performance.

Based on the performance theory above, the object of this research was carried out at RSD dr. Soebandi Jember. Based on the Decree of the Governor of East Java number 188/359/KPTS/013/2015 concerning the implementation of the regional reference factor for East Java Province, RSD dr. Soebandi Jember has been designated as a referral hospital for Jember Regency, Situbondo Regency, Bondowoso Regency, Banyuwangi Regency, Lumajang Regency, Probolinggo City and Probolinggo Regency. RSD dr. Soebandi Jember is an organization operating in the service sector that has a close relationship with human resource management. The resources in the hospital consist of health personnel including doctors, nurses, pharmacists, analysts, nutritionists, physiotherapists, radiographers, medical recorders and non-health personnel such as finance, administration, personnel, security and so on. Based on the nurse performance report, it can be seen that the performance target for nurses at RSD dr. Soebandi Jember by 100%. However, performance achievement in each performance indicator is only 85% of the predetermined target. Based on performance report data, it can be concluded that nurses' performance achievements have not been able to reach the specified targets. Referring to this phenomenon, the researchers took the initiative to provide a

solution to this problem by referring to factors that are assumed to be important for improving nurse performance, including work experience and competency of nurses in carrying out their duties at RSD Dr. Soebandi Jember. Based on the results of previous research related to work experience variables and also employee competency which is linked to performance, there are still results that are not in accordance with theory. Therefore, it is important to carry out this research with the first objective, namely to determine the impact of work experience on employee performance and the second objective, namely to determine the impact of employee competency on employee performance for nurses at RSD Dr. Soebandi Jember.

RESEARCH METHODS

Research was carried out using a quantitative approach emphasizing analysis of numerical data (numbers) which were then analyzed using appropriate methods. The population in this study were all nurses at RSD dr. Soebandi, numbering 463 people. The sampling technique or method used was stratified random sampling, totaling 150 people. Research variables can be identified as exogenous variables including work experience (X1) and nurse competency (X2). The endogenous variable is performance (Y). Respondent descriptions were carried out to determine the scope of respondents in this research. Validity tests and reliability tests are always carried out so that the measuring instruments used are valid and reliable. Direct influence analysis was also carried out by hypothesis testing.

RESULTS

Descriptive Results of Demographics of Research Respondents

The research respondent was an RSD nurse, Dr. Soebandi Jember Regency as many as 150 people. An overview of the demographic statistics of respondents shows that the number of female respondents is greater than male respondents, namely 67.33% or 101 people. Based on the results of the respondents, it can be seen that the age range of around 36-40 is seen at 24%, so the age in this range is dominant. Based on the educational level of the respondents in this study, the S1 level of education had a value of 59% for 88 respondents.

Data Validity Test Results

The validity of the data in this research is measured by the loading factor value. The criterion for the loading factor value is 0.7. The validity value of the data in this study is presented in Table 1 below.

Table 1. Indicator Loading Factor Values

Indicator	Work Experience (X1)	Competence X2	Employee Performance (Y)	P value
X1.1	0,832	-0,478	-0,125	<0,001
X1.2	0,877	0,053	0,069	<0,001
X1.3	0,855	0,411	0,051	<0,001
X2.1	-0,160	0,909	0,359	<0,001
X2.2	0,164	0,932	-0,269	<0,001
X2.3	-0,008	0,951	-0,079	<0,001
Y1.1	-0,165	-0,012	0,898	<0,001
Y1.2	-0,045	-0,156	0,908	<0,001
Y1.3	0,029	-0,316	0,910	<0,001
Y1.4	-0,075	0,281	0,789	<0,001
Y1.5	0,310	0,545	0,802	0,005
Y1.6	0,196	0,135	0,809	<0,001

The results of the analysis show that all research variable indicators have a loading factor value above 0.7 so they are considered to meet the value of data validity.

Data Reliability Test Results

The purpose of reliability testing is to ensure that the research instruments used can provide consistent

measurement of concepts. The measuring value for testing data reliability is by looking at the Cronbach's alpha value. The criteria for Cronbach's alpha value is above 0.6. The results of the data reliability values in this study are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Reliability Test Results

Variable of Research	Cronbach's alpha	Results
Work Experience (X1)	0,816	Meet Reliability
Competence X2	0,923	Meet Reliability
Employee Performance (Y)	0,856	Meet Reliability

The reliability test results presented in the table appear to meet the requirements of a reliability test, because they have a value above 0.6.

Direct Effect Testing

In this direct influence test, each path tested shows the direct influence of work experience (X1) and

competency (X2) and employee performance (Y) of nurses at RSD dr. Soebandi, Jember Regency. Hypothesis testing is aimed at whether the hypothesis presented can be accepted or not. In Table 3, the results are displayed.

Table 3. Hypothesis Results

No	Hypothesis	Path coefficients	P-values	Informations
1.	Work Experience (X1) → Employee Performance (Y)	0,686	0,001	H1 Accepted
2	Competence X2 → Employee Performance (Y)	0,144	0,012	H2 Accepted

DISCUSSION

The Influence of Work Experience on Nurse Performance

Based on the test results and data analysis, the coefficient value of the work experience variable (X1) is 0.686 with a p value of 0.001. The first hypothesis (H1) of this research is that work experience influences employee performance at RSD dr. Soebandi Jember. It turns out that

after the analysis was carried out, the first hypothesis (H1) was accepted and H0 was rejected. Thus, it can be concluded that nurses' work experience can have a positive and significant influence on the employee performance of nurses at RSD Dr. Soebandi, Jember Regency. This is proven to be true or H1 is accepted. Work experience is needed to increase the effectiveness of human resources within the company, the aim of this is to obtain effective

work results and increase work productivity for the employees themselves. The longer an employee works for a company, the more experience the employee has (Bili et al., 2018; Dash et al., 2017; Rivaldo & Nabella, 2023). Apart from expert opinion, this research hypothesis was built based on empirical evidence conducted by (Arifin & Putra, 2020; Dewanti & Artaya, 2019; Kim et al., 2009; Masriah, 2021; Prasetya, 2018; Sinambela & Ernawati, 2021), the results Research shows that a lot of work experience can improve employee performance optimally.

The Influence of Competency on Nurse Performance

Based on the results of testing and data analysis in the second hypothesis, competency influences employee performance, stating that competency has a significant influence on employee performance by RSD Nurse Dr. Soebandi, Jember Regency. This is proven to be true or H2 is accepted. A nurse's performance can be seen through several aspects, one of which is the skills and accurate information she has, a nurse who is fast and responsive. This is closely related to their competency as a nurse where they have expertise in their respective fields. This expertise means insight as well as technical expertise. With good competency, this will be in line with the nurse's performance becoming better. Several studies show various research results that refer to research (Puspitasari et al., 2024), (Galih et al., 2023), (Hendrawan & Sanosra, 2023), (Qomariah & Utamy, 2023), (A. Setiawan et al., 2023), (Rahmadani et al., 2020), (Qomariah et al., 2023), (Hapsari et al., 2022), (Sukowidodo et al., 2022), (A. Wahyudi et al., 2022), (Rusmayanti et al., 2022), (Setiawan et al., 2022), (Mustikawati & Qomariah, 2020), research results show that competence has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. Meanwhile, research results that are not in line with this research are those conducted by (Kurniawan et al., 2021), (Utomo et al., 2019) competence does not have a positive and significant effect on employee performance.

CONCLUSIONS, SUGGESTIONS, IMPLICATIONS

The results of the research after the analysis were carried out were that the work experience of nurses at RSD dr. Soebandi Jember can improve employee performance. The next result is that the competencies possessed by RSD nurses, Dr. Soebandi Jember can provide significant performance improvements.

Looking at the conclusions from this research, the advice that needs to be conveyed is to the hospital to continue to provide improvements to the work experience and competency of nurses so that the performance of nurses continues to improve and can compete with other hospitals. For future research, it is hoped that other variables such as OCB and work culture can be used.

It is hoped that the implications of this research can contribute to thinking about human resource management,

especially regarding issues of work experience, competency and employee performance.

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